

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

TECHNOLOGY OF MASTERING MATERIALS FOR THE TEACHING UNIT "ELEMENTS OF STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY THEORY" IN THE XI GRADE OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the content of the skills intended to become the subject of students in the process of teaching materials for the "Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" educational unit, which is included in the content of the Mathematics subject in the XI classes of general education schools, is presented. In the "Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" teaching unit, the content elements that perform the "enabling function" in the formation of the mentioned skills and attention is focused on the technology of turning them into action in the students' cognition. "Statistics and Elements of probability theory" of the elements that are transformed in the educational unit "Statistical indicators: dispersion and standard deviation", "Forms of data distribution. Normal distribution", "Box - handle diagram", "Coincidence and Probability" it is considered appropriate to make it into a system on topics. It should be noted that the task system, which plays the role of a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements presented by the students, should contain the verbs required to be performed in the topics. Examples of tasks of that kind are included in the content of the work.

Keywords: statistics; statistical indicators; likely; theory; element; normal distribution; dispersion; standard deviation; chart; random events; event space; testing; teaching process; teaching unit; content lines; standard; system; methodical system; "system-structure" approach; paradigm.

Relevance of the topic. One of the important theories in the field of pedagogy is didactics. The change of socio-economic formations and the replacement of industrial revolutions have made the educational space compatible with the flow of civilization. According to the mentioned logic, human experience has been enriched, new forms of its transmission from generation to generation have appeared, the theory of education and training has been adequately perfected to the level of development of scientific cognition. In didactics, in subject methodologies, which are its important fields, the principles, rules, and recommendations that are useful for guiding the teacher's activities have been brought to the fore. In accordance with that process, there are recommendations that are useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the currently used textbook complex and various educational literature about teaching units, basic standards, sub-standards, and defined topics in the subject of Mathematics. This is very useful in terms of teaching the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is logical, most didactic problems are eternal. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system of the teaching process adequate to it should be improved. Based on this logic, "Statistics and Elements of probability theory" We claim the relevance of the study of the topic "Methodical system of teaching the specified subjects for the realization of sub-standards for the educational unit (XI class).

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research.

Scientific sources indicate that "training" and "educational activity" are one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. By the way, let's emphasize that to get to the essence of these and many other pedagogical concepts, to give an honest scientific interpretation, based on the idea of L. Bertalanfi, is a successful approach, in our opinion, the "system-structural approach" is a branch of dialectics that has developed and gained the "status" of independence.[9; 8]

Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different activities. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity.[1;150]

The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources leads us to the conclusion that training is a way of implementing education, and the fact that spiritual education, memorization of knowledge and the acquisition of experience of creative activity based on this depends on the way of education (dialectic of the content and form of cognitive action). The formation of the educational implementation model in didactics is a perennial problem. [10]

The education of the current era plays a greater role in the formation of a person as a creative personality with its cognitive character. For this purpose, educational approaches adequate to the challenges of the most modern-IV industrial revolution, which is spreading widely in the world, are used. As one of the coun-

tries with independent, consistent and systematic development principles of our time, work is being done in this direction in Azerbaijan. A personality-oriented education system is established, which includes results according to the demands and needs of the society. In the rapidly modernizing Republic of Azerbaijan, taking the necessary steps to meet the challenges of human capital development and adapting the quality indicators of general education to European standards, restructuring the education management system to improve the quality of education, developing human resources in this field and increasing the reputation of the teaching profession have been the focus of attention. It is aimed that the education system should form citizens who have mastered the national values of independent and sovereign Azerbaijan, and should train creative and creative thinking personalities with competitive, professional competencies and knowledge in the globalized and modern world.

Experience shows that although the system of training, which is a way of implementing education, consisting of goals, content, form, methods and means, has always been leading, approaches to it have varied. The fact that the listed important components are not connected in a strategic line and do not obey the relevant principles has made it difficult to understand their dialectical connection and limited the possibilities of application in the real pedagogical process. I know that it is necessary to emphasize that the application of the curriculum model in our education system made it possible to bring the mentioned components to one channel, to establish them on one line. As a result, a unified structure with a network of components was formed.[10]

Currently, a special document covering the content of various activities in education has appeared. The peculiarity of this document is that it is conceptual in nature, combining training content, strategies, evaluation mechanisms and so on. It plays the role of a base in the creation of all resources, organization and management of the training process, and directs the activities of people, starting from the compilers of the textbooks to all specialists involved in evaluation in the training process. The organization and implementation of all activities related to the curriculum training process, i.e. necessary competencies for students, content and assessment standards, curriculum and programs, requirements for the student (student) and his level, specific developmental goals of each lesson, methodological provision, evaluation model, technical equipment, etc. it is understood as a conceptual document that contains the tasks facing the teacher and the school and shows their specific solutions.

According to our subjective understanding, the subject curricula applied in our schools have a perfect system-structure in terms of answering all the questions posed in the direction of organizing the training process in the subject to which it belongs, which is efficient and constantly developing, useful and directed to the final result, with modern methods. In the training process based on this model, it is not difficult to expect the demand for constructivism and corporatism, the situation

of "opportunity-action-new quality" can be ensured in the mentioned process.

The content, strategy, and evaluation mechanism contained in any subject curriculum makes it possible to expect the dialectic of subsystems and components of the educational system. Assessing student achievement is an ongoing, dynamic, and often informal process.

It includes components such as assessment data, data collection, assessment results and assessment standards as a means of effective feedback between assessment-learning outcomes and stakeholders as a systematic process. The results of a properly conducted evaluation allow to make decisions about the teacher's activity, how well this activity meets the needs of students, and the need to make appropriate changes in the curriculum, planning and lessons. Assessment and learning processes can be seen as two interacting aspects of education.

The technology of education implementation (methodology in the traditional approach) has its own system. The expected result in the mentioned technological system is determined by the state of movement of the selected content. A technological system is available for each educational unit. It is not accidental that the selection of the teaching unit is brought to the center of attention when designing the mentioned system.[4-5]

The main and sub-content standards of knowledge that are important to master in the teaching unit "Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" in the XI grade of a general education school are:

5.1. Collects, systematizes, analyzes and presents statistical information;

5.1.1. Calculates the variance and mean square criterion of the measurement;

5.2. Understands and applies the basic concepts of probability theory;

5.2.1. Applies the law of normal distribution to the calculation of the probability of the event.

"Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" In the process of teaching the topics covered in the educational unit, students are expected to acquire the following skills (see: [8; 214--227]):

- It presents the data according to statistical indicators that characterize the distribution, such as numerical mean, median, mode, central tendency, and the largest difference;

- Calculates the trend, dispersion, standard deviation according to the given data base in various forms;

- Explains by showing examples the understanding of the relationship between the value of the standard deviation and the distribution of data values;

- Constructs a normal distribution curve according to the sample (population) and presents it according to the situation;

- It presents the information graphically according to the numerical mean and standard deviation in the normal distribution;

- Identifies and presents data according to the conditions required in the normal distribution with calculations;

- Solves problems related to probability according to the normal distribution curve;
- Divides the data into quartiles;
- Presents data with a threaded box diagram;
- Demonstrates understanding of concepts such as random event, space of random events, trial, event;
- Applies probabilities to the calculation of cumulative and non-combinable events;
- Applies the rule of multiplying probabilities to the occurrence of independent events;
- Applies conditional probability formula to problem solving;

Mastering the materials of the "Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" educational unit, students' active mathematical vocabulary includes the following concepts - population, selection, numerical mean, mode, median, tendency, mean square deviation, dispersion, box-handle diagram, event, random event, experiment, elementary event, space of elementary events, independent events, dependent events, conditional probability and allows to be enriched with considerations related to them.

It is recommended to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course [11-16]) and various worksheets as additional resources in teaching the materials of the "Elements of Statistics and Probability Theory" educational unit.

It is enough to devote 2 hours to the teaching of the subject "Statistics: dispersion and standard deviation" at the beginning of the teaching of the subject "Statistics: dispersion and standard deviation" in order to master the concepts of "Dispersion" and "standard deviation" for students to learn about the "number" used to analyze statistical data. Reproduction of necessary parts of the content of training materials on "mean", "mode", "median" is carried out. For this purpose, it is recommended to benefit from the application of reproductive studies and heuristic methods. Students remember that they used "numerical mean", "mode", and "median" indicators to analyze statistical data. They know that the numerical mean is found by using the values of all data, and that outliers affect its value and can lead to wrong conclusions about the population. Median is the middle value of data arranged in ascending order. The median divides the data into two halves—lower and upper halves. It is a more reliable statistic in a population where outliers exist. Useful for analyzing a limited amount of data. Mode defines the characteristic information for the collection. It allows you to think about the numerical mean and is more convenient for the analysis of categorical data (gender, color, etc.). Data may or may not have more than one mode. [8; 215].

Summarizing the restorative activities of the students, the teacher informs the students that in order to draw more correct results according to statistical data,

indicators such as tendency, dispersion, and standard deviation are used to characterize them.

"The deviation is defined as the difference between the value of the data and the mean. It is represented as $x_{meyil} = x - \bar{x}$, where x is the given numerical value of the data and $\bar{x}$ is the mean. Variance is defined as the ratio of the sum of the squares of the deviations to the number of data values and is denoted by σ^2 ."

$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n}$, where n is the number of values of information. The standard tendency is called the square root of the variance and is usually denoted by the letter σ - "sigma": $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma^2}$.

The standard deviation is an important statistic that characterizes the distribution of data. The standard deviation shows the distribution of data values according to the numerical mean, and the farther apart the data values are, the greater the standard deviation. The closer the data values are to each other, the smaller the standard deviation. In other words, if the mean number is concentrated around the mean, the standard deviation is small. [7; 261].

The teacher should use sample tasks (see [7; 262-263]) in order to regulate the environment for deeper assimilation of this information given to students. This is an approach tested by practitioners, its effectiveness is not in doubt.

An example. The weekly salary of 10 randomly selected employees in the company is as follows: 120, 160, 90, 175, 110, 80, 220, 150, 300, 95 manats. Calculate the mean, variance, and standard deviation for this data and explain the situation.

Solution:

1. Let's make a table according to the salaries.
2. Let's calculate the numerical average: $\bar{x} = 1400:10 = 140$.
3. By subtracting the numerical average from each salary amount, its deviation from the numerical average is found.

For example, $120-140 = -20$, This person's salary is 20 Manats less than the average weekly salary. Let's add a column to the table indicating the inclination ($x_i - \bar{x}$) for each salary. The sum of the trends of the individual data is equal to zero. This is always the case and does not provide new information. Therefore, the sum of the squares of the trends is used.

4. Let's calculate each $(x_i - \bar{x})^2$ and record it in a new column in the table and find the sum: $\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 = 43150$.

To calculate the variance, divide the sum ($n = 10$) we find by the number of data n .

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(x_i-\bar{x})^2}{n} = \frac{43150}{10} = 4315.$$

Salary	Tendency: $(x_1 - \bar{x})$	Square: $(x_1 - \bar{x})^2$
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Numerical average $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x_i}{n} = 140$

120	-20	400
160	20	400
90	-50	2500
175	35	1225
110	-30	900
80	-60	3600
220	80	6400
150	10	100
300	160	25600
95	-45	2025
Total: $\sum x_i = 1400$	Total: $\sum (x_i - \bar{x}) = 0$	Total: $\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$

5. To find the standard deviation of salaries, take the square root of the variance: $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma^2} = \sqrt{4315} \approx 65,69$

Students are explained that according to the standard tendency, the change in salaries can be assessed. For example, a person who receives a salary of 300 manat receives more than the average weekly salary (140 manat) than the 2 standard incline (2×65). A person who receives a weekly salary of 90 Manats receives a salary of about one standard inclination (65) less than a weekly salary.

It is recommended to apply a system of tasks made into a special system for students to master the theoretical materials related to the topic "Statistical indicators: dispersion and standard deviation", to include them in the existing experience base and to develop relevant skills in students..We consider it appropriate to include the following task examples in the mentioned system [3; 447-450].

1. Perform the tasks according to the given information.

100; 200; 300; 400; 500; 600; 700; 800; 900; 1000.

a) Find the numerical mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation (σ)

b) Multiply each data value by 10. Find the mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation (σ) for the new data.

c) Divide the value of each data by 10. $\bar{x}$ and find σ .

d) Discuss your thoughts about the results. Explain whether the numerical mean is the right indicator to evaluate the situation compared to the value of the standard deviation.

2. The results of 8 girls and 8 boys randomly selected from among the SAT (Scholastic Aptitude Test) examinees are as follows.

Boys' SAT scores: 1059; 1328; 1175; 1123; 923; 1017; 1214; 1042.

Girls' SAT scores: 1226; 965; 841; 1053; 1056; 1393; 1312; 1222.

a) Find the largest variance, variance, and standard deviation for each group of data.

b) Explain the result according to the real situation.

3. Find the largest variance, mean, variance, and standard deviation that fit the data.

a) 11; 10; 11; 7; 8; 11; 6; 4; 6; 7

b) 13; 15; 13; 17; 18; 13; 15; 14; 13; 20; 20; 18; 23; 20. And so on.

"Forms of information distribution. Normal distribution" it is enough to spend 2 hours teaching the subject. "Forms of information distribution. "Normal distribution" topic students are given information in the following content.

According to the shape of the frequency distribution, suitable graphic forms (histogram or frequency polygon) can be symmetrical or asymmetrical:

1. Normal distribution; 2. Right-skewed distribution (positive distribution); 3. Left-skewed distribution (negative distribution).

We can say about the normal distribution:

*The normal distribution curve is symmetric with respect to the numerical mean:

*In a normal distribution, the number is equal to the mean, median, and mode;

*The graph of the normal distribution is constructed according to the numerical mean and standard deviation "The normal distribution mainly reflects data around three standard deviations. $\bar{x} \pm 3\sigma$)

The normal distribution is also called the 68-95-99 distribution. ■

The graph of the normal distribution shifts to the right or left depending on the value of the numerical mean. The graph is compressed or stretched by changing the standard deviation at the same value of the numerical mean.

In the process of teaching the subject, students are involved in learning tasks made into a system, and the normal distribution form is mastered by them.

First, in order to visualize the form of normal distribution, students are involved in the following example

An example. In a normal distribution corresponding to any x value, the numerical mean is 40, and the standard trend is 5. What percentage of the prices included in this collection:

a) Is it less than 45? b) It is between 30 and 45.

After the implementation of the example, it is useful to continue the process of teaching the subject by engaging students in several learning tasks as follows.

1. It is known that the numerical mean is 72 (points) and the standard deviation is 6 (points) in the normal distribution according to the test.

1) Write down the following information: a) numbers located around 1 standard deviation from the

mean; b) those located around 2 standard deviations from the numerical mean; c) those located around 3 standard deviations from the numerical mean; 2) Draw a curve fitting a normal distribution. Show each interval as a percentage.

2. Plot normal distribution curves in the same coordinate system. Explain the similarities and differences between these graphs.

a) numerical average 50 percent, standard trend 10 numerical average 50 percent, standard trend 20 **b) numerical average 50 percent, standard trend 5 numerical average 40 percent, standard trend 5**

3. The exam results were presented with a normal distribution. According to the results, the numerical average is 70, the standard deviation is 4.5. 360 people participated in the exam.

1) If a random person is selected, he/she:

a) the possibility of being among those who scored in the range of 65-80;

b) the possibility of being among those who scored not less than 75 points;

c) Find the probability that he is among those who scored less than 62.

2) Calculate the range in which 90% of test-takers scored.

"Box - Handle Diagram" it is enough to spend 2 hours teaching the subject. How to construct a box-handle diagram It is explained to the students according to the following example [7; 270-273].

Example. Scores of 15 employees in the company during the safety standards exam: 13; 9; 18; 15; 14; 21; 7; 10; 11; 20; 5; 18; 37; 16; It was like 17. Present this information with a box-and-handle diagram.

1. The median is determined by arranging the data in ascending order and is marked with Q_2

($Q_2 = 15$);

2. The data on the left side of the median is the lower part, and the data on the right side is the upper part. That is, the median divides the data into two parts.

3. The medians of the halves, called quartiles (here, divides the data into 4 parts. $Q_1 = 10$, $Q_3 = 18$)

4. Interquartile variation is determined: $Q_3 - Q_1 = 18 - 10 = 8$.

5. The smallest and largest values of the information given on the number axis, the values of the quartiles and the median - 5 important points are noted. A rectangle whose length is equal to the interquartile variation is drawn. This rectangle is divided into two parts by the median. the handles of the box are pulled (the explained steps should be accompanied by visuals, otherwise the steps taken will be difficult for students to understand).

Thus, a box-handle diagram is constructed according to the given data. According to the diagram, the data is presented as follows: about half of the 15 people, 50% scored between 10 and 18. 25% scored less than 10, 25% scored more than 10.

The difference in the length of the left and right handle depends on the difference in the values of the information in the corresponding part.

The activity on the sample is summarized.

When constructing the box-handle diagram, 5 data are determined according to the given value: median - Q_2 , median of the lower half, where the data smaller than the median is collected-quartile Q_1 , median of the upper half, where the data larger than the median is collected-quartile Q_3 , smallest value and largest value. [6; 181-183].

Steps to construct a box-and-handle diagram:

1. A horizontal straight line is drawn.

2. Divisions with a certain scale are set according to the data variation range.

3. Determined 5 data - Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , the smallest value, the largest value - are recorded on a straight line.

4. A box is drawn up Q_1 to Q_3

5. From the smallest price to Q_1 and from Q_3 to the largest price, the handles are pulled.

Students are engaged in cognitive activity on another example, as follows lays the foundation for a more sophisticated mastery of the steps of constructing a box-and-handle diagram.

An example. The ages of the members of the Paralympic women's volleyball team are as follows: 24; 30; 30; 22; 25; 22; 18; 25; 28; 30; 25; 27. Present the data with a box-and-handle diagram.

"Box-handle diagram", it is recommended to master the building steps by the students, to include them in the existing experience base and to apply a system of tasks made into a special system for the development of the relevant skills in the students.

"Random Events and Probability" it is enough to devote 4 hours to the teaching of the subject. On the topic "Random events and probability". students are given information in the following content [7; 274].

The branch of mathematics that studies the regularity of random events is called probability theory. This theory studies not individual events, but the results of numerous experiments, that is, the regularities of massive random events. Probability is a mathematical-numerical characteristic of the possibility of a certain event occurring under certain conditions.

A probable event is certain to occur as a result of experiment, experiment, or observation, and an impossible event never occurs. Events are conventionally interpreted as complex (separable) and elementary (non-separable) events. Each inseparable result of an experiment, experiment or observation is called an elementary event. The set of all elementary events is called the space of elementary events or test space. All possible outcomes of a particular experiment or observation

$E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n$ the space of elementary events if it has elementary events $U = \{E_1, \dots, E_n\}$ can to any subset

of the space of elementary events **event" is said. At this time** "the empty set ($\emptyset$) impossible event, U and it will probably be an event. Since each event is a subset of the space of elementary events, the actions defined for sets are defined for events in the same way:

- An event in which all outcomes include at least one of events A or B is called a combination of events A and B and is denoted by $A \cup B$.

- An event whose outcomes include both event A and event B is called the intersection of events A and B and is denoted as $A \cap B$.

• Events that do not have common outcomes are called incompatible events.

• The set of all outcomes not included in event A is called the opposite event of event A and is denoted as $\bar{A}$.

• If every consequence of event A is also a consequence of event B, event A is said to cause event B, or event B is a consequence of event A, and this fact $A \subset B$ It is written as.

• An event whose results are not included in event B, but only included in event A, is called the difference between event A and event B. Denoted as $A \setminus B$. [3; 454].

Students in secondary schools in the process of teaching mathematics in a series of tests **frequency** is introduced to the concept. They understand that if we denote the total number of trials by n and the number of trials in which event A occurs during n trials by $n(A)$, $\frac{n(A)}{n}$ The ratio is called the frequency of event A in

this series of trials. The probability of a random event can be approximated by the frequency of a series of

multiple trials: $P(A) \approx \frac{n(A)}{n}$

$P(A)$ the probability does not depend on whether the test is passed or not, this number characterizes the random event A. The probability of a random event is the number to which the values of the observed frequency converge during numerous trials. Such a definition of probability is called a statistical definition.

It should be clear to the students that the elementary events of the test occurring under the same conditions and under the same conditions are called equally likely events if one has no advantage over the other.

The ratio of the number of favorable outcomes for event A to the number of all equally likely events is called the probability of event A and is denoted by

$P(A): P(A) = \frac{n(A)}{n}$ (1). This definition is called the

classical definition of the probability of an event.

$0 \leq n(A) \leq n$ since it follows from formula (1) that

$0 \leq P(A) \leq 1$ $E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n$ if all events are favora-

ble to event A, i.e. if $n(A)=n$, then $P(A) = \frac{n}{n} = 1$

Probably the probability of the event is equal to 1. If neither outcome is favorable to event A, that is, if A is an impossible event, then $n(A)=0$ and $P(A)=0$. The probability of an impossible event is zero. Here it is useful to bring the following property to the attention of students.

Property. Equally possible $E_1, \dots, E_n$ elementary events have the same probability and the sum of these probabilities is equal to 1.

Indeed, suppose event A $E_1, \dots, E_n$ coincides with one of the events, e.g. $A = E_1$ is. Then $E_i \cap E_j = \emptyset$ since $i \neq j$ when $A \neq E_j$ happens. So,

$n(A) = n(E_1) = 1$. According to formula (1).

$P(A) = P(E_1) = \frac{1}{n}$. A similar rule shows that

$P(E_2) = \frac{1}{n}, \dots, P(E_n) = \frac{1}{n}$; From here it follows

that $P(E_1) + P(E_2) + \dots + P(E_n) = 1$

The given theoretical information should be clarified by special studies. Let's give examples [6; 187-190].

1. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in the box. Find the probability that a ball drawn at random is black.

Solution: The number of possible cases is $n=10+15=25$, the number of favorable cases is $m=15$. Therefore, if we denote the event of black ball removal by A, $P(A) = \frac{15}{25} = \frac{3}{5}$

2. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in the box. Taking a ball out of the box and suppose that the ball is black. Let's put it aside and take a ball out of the box. Let's find the probability that this ball is also black.

Solution: Since the first ball removed is black, there are 10 white and 14 black balls left in the box. Therefore, the number of possible cases is $n=24$, and the number of favorable cases is $m=14$. For the second time, if we mark the event of black ball extraction with B, $P(B) = \frac{14}{24} = \frac{7}{12}$

3. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in the box. Two balls are drawn from the box at a time. Find the probability that both balls are black.

Solution: Let us denote the case when both globules are black with A. The number of possible cases when removing two globules at once $n = C_{25}^2 = \frac{25 \cdot 24}{1 \cdot 2} = 300$, number of favorable cases $m = C_{15}^2 = \frac{15 \cdot 14}{1 \cdot 2} = 105$. So, $P(A) = \frac{105}{300} = \frac{7}{20}$.

4. There are 7 white, 5 red and 8 yellow balls in the box. Let us denote the event of a drawn ball being white by A, the event that it is red by Q, and the event that it is yellow by S, and find the probability of each of these events.

Solution: It is clear that the number of possible cases is $n = 7 + 5 + 8 = 20$, and the number of favorable cases for each of these events is $m_A = 7m_Q = 5m_S = 8$, respectively. Therefore,

$$P(A) = \frac{7}{20}, P(Q) = \frac{5}{20} = \frac{1}{4}, P(S) = \frac{8}{20} = \frac{2}{5}.$$

5. The coin is tossed twice. In both cases, you have to find the probability that the face with the coat of arms falls.

The solution. Let us mark the fall of the face with a number by "r", and the fall of the face with a coat of arms by "g". When the coin is tossed twice, the equally possible (equally probable) cases are: (rr), (rg), (gr), (gg). Therefore, the number of possible cases is $n=4$, and the number of favorable cases for the coat of arms falling in both cases is $m=1$. Therefore, in both cases, the probability of the face falling is $p = \frac{1}{4}$.

6. While inspecting a batch of 200 identical parts, the technical control department discovered 6 non-standard parts. Let's find the probability that a detail drawn at random is not standard.

Solution: The number of possible cases is $n = 200$, and the number of favorable cases is $m = 6$. Therefore,

$$p = \frac{6}{200} = \frac{3}{100}.$$

7. The probability of hitting the target with a pistol shot is 0.75. If 200 shots are fired, how many bullets can be expected to hit the target?

Solution: In the issue, the probability of hitting the target and the number of possible cases are given: $p=0.75$, $n=200$. According to the classical definition of probability, it should be $0.75=m/200$. From here, $m=200 \cdot 0.75 = 150$.

So, with a probability of 0.75, one can expect that out of 200 shots, 150 will hit the target.

Students should know that they calculate the probability of a complex event by dividing it into events with known probabilities. As is known, $U = \{E_1, \dots, E_n\}$ each of the space of elementary events E_k element is called its probability and is not exactly $P(E_k)$ numerically opposed that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n P(E_k) = P(E_1) + \dots + P(E_n) = 1$$

condition is paid. Then, U - or probability space is called. Probability space $(E_1, \dots, E_n; P_1, \dots, P_n)$ or (U, P) is marked as It follows that for every $k, 0 \leq P(E_k); k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Since each event A is a certain subset of the space of elementary events, it has a separation over elementary events, that is, a certain E_{k_p} for elementary phenomena

$A = \bigcup_p E_{k_p}$ happens. The probability $P(A)$ of the event A is called the sum of the probabilities of elementary events in its division by elementary events.

$$P(A) = P\left(\bigcup_p E_{k_p}\right) = \sum_p P(E_{k_p})$$

$$P(A) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(A|B_i)P(B_i) = P(A|B_1) \cdot P(B_1) + \dots + P(A|B_n) \cdot P(B_n)$$

is correct. This formula is called the complete probability formula.

$$0 < P(B) < 1 \text{ when}$$

$$P(A) = P(A|B) \cdot P(B) + P(A|\bar{B}) \cdot P(\bar{B}).$$

In order to achieve the expected result in the process of teaching mathematics, students should be familiar with the concept of independent events. They are informed by the following.

Suppose that A and B are two different nonempty events of the space of elementary events. If the occurrence of event A does not depend on the occurrence of event B , then

$P(A|B) = P(A)$ we can write (assuming that $P(B) > 0$). Then the conditional probability

It is useful to familiarize students with the following theorems, which are [3; 457-459] plays an important role in probability theory

Theorem 1. a) any anesthetic $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$ for events $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B)$; b) $P(\emptyset) = 0$ c) $A \subset U, B \subset U$ and $A \subset B$ for any events A and B satisfying their relations $P(A) \leq P(B)$; d) any $A \subset U$ the same is paid for the event and its opposite $\bar{A}$ event $P(A) = 1 - P(\bar{A})$; e) any $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$ for events $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$ attitude is correct.

The property of the theorem in clause a) can be summarized as follows: pairwise discontinuous $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n$ the probability of the combination of events is equal to the sum of their probabilities, that is, while $i \neq j$ when $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$. This property is called the property of summation of probabilities.

This is a positive probability event, and A is any event $P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}$ the quantity is called the

conditional probability of the event A under the condition of occurrence of the event B . It follows that $P(A \cap B) = P(A) \cdot P(B|A)$. This property is called the property of multiplication of probabilities.

Theorem 2. U is a space of elementary events with equal possibilities. Certain $B \subset U$ any within the condition of occurrence of the event $A \subset U$ conditional probability of an event $P(A|B) = \frac{n(A \cap B)}{n(B)}$

is found by the formula.

Theorem 3. U the space of elementary phenomena is not matched in pairs $B_1, \dots, B_n$ separated by events, namely: $U = B_1 \cup \dots \cup B_n$ and $i \neq j$ for $B_i \cap B_j = \emptyset$. Then, for any event A

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}$$

$$P(A \cap B) = P(B) \cdot P(A|B); \text{ Events } A \text{ and } B$$

$P(A \cap B) = P(B) \cdot P(A|B)$ when they satisfy the relation they are called independent events.

It should be noted here that this definition $P(B) = 0$ in the case, that is $P(A|B)$ is true even if the conditional probability is not specified. If events A and B are independent, known $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$ formula $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A) \cdot P(B)$ can be written as

Any $k = 1, \dots, n$ and $i \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq n$ for $P(A_{i_1} \cap \dots \cap A_{i_k}) = P(A_{i_1}) \cdot \dots \cdot (P(A_{i_k}))$ when paid $A_1, \dots, A_n$ a system of events is called a system that is independent of the totality. $A_1, \dots, A_n$ in the case of a system that is independent of the whole, in the special case, $P(A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n) = P(A_1) \cdot \dots \cdot (P(A_n))$ the probability multiplication formula is obtained.

As it is known, according to the classical definition of probability, to find the probability of event A in a given problem, it is enough to divide the number of elements of A (the number of "favorable cases") by the total number of elements appearing in the considered problem (the number of "possible cases"). Finding the number of favorable and feasible cases when looking at phenomena with finite element results is, in many cases, possible through the application of combination theory. In this direction, a task system should be applied for the purpose of forming students' skills. The following can be used as an example.

1. There are 9 rows in the auditorium of the cinema, and 9 seats in each row. The audience takes a random seat. Is it more likely that the sum of the numbers of the row and the place in the row is even or odd? (sum even probability is greater),

2. (Selection by return). In the box 1,2,...there are n globules numbered with N numbers. k times a pellet is accidentally removed from the box, its number is recorded and returned back to the box. Find the probability of the event that all the elements of the selection are diverse. $(P(B) = \frac{n(B)}{n(U)} = \frac{A_n^k}{n^k})$

$$P(B) = \frac{n(B)}{n(U)} = \frac{A_n^k}{n^k}$$

3. In the box 1,2,...there are n spheres numbered with N numbers. The Spheres are taken out of the box one by one, carefully mixing. Spheres 1,2,...find the probability that it will turn out in the sequence with the

$$P = \frac{1}{P_n} = \frac{1}{n!}$$

4. There are n globules of the same shape in the box. Their number k is red, and the rest is blue. An M sphere is accidentally removed from the box. Find the probability of the event that the sphere l is red within

$$P = \frac{C_k^l \cdot C_{n-k}^{m-l}}{C_n^m}$$

5. They threw a point inside the Egyptian triangle. Find the probability that the point is at a distance greater than 1 from the sides of the triangle.

It should be noted that these types of problems are also called geometric probability problems, and the ratio of the size of the G area (length, area, volume) to the size of the D area is taken as the probability of the event of the fall of an object thrown into a certain D area to the area located in this area. The answer to this task:

$$P = \frac{6 - \frac{\pi}{2}}{6} = 1 - \frac{\pi}{12}$$

"Elements of probability theory" it is recommended to use the summative evaluation criteria listed below for the educational unit.

1. The data is presented according to statistical indicators characterizing the distribution, such as numerical mean, median, mode, central tendency, and the largest difference.

2. It calculates the trend, dispersion, standard deviation according to the given database in various forms.

3. Constructs a normal distribution curve for the sample (population) and presents it according to the situation.

4. Determines and presents data according to the conditions required in the normal distribution with calculations.

5. Presents the information with a box-handle diagram.

6. Demonstrates understanding of concepts such as test, event, space of elementary events, random event.

7. Applies the rule of adding probabilities to the calculation of probabilities of events.

8. Applies the rule of multiplying probabilities to calculating the probabilities of independent events.

9. It resolves issues related to conditional probability.

The result. 1) Pedagogical practice has proven that the content and system of tasks play a determining role in the acquisition of necessary skills by students in educational institutions. Therefore, "Statistics and Elements of Probability Theory" in the process of teaching the topics covered in the educational unit, the selection and application of task types should be kept in the center of attention so that students become subjects of the verbs based on the expected results;

2) One of the main tasks in general education schools is the formation of creative personalities. Realization of this important task requires the development of memory, thinking and speech as parts of a unit. Therefore, "Statistics and Elements of probability theory" the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of students' active mathematical vocabulary in the process of teaching materials for the educational unit should be considered as an important didactic requirement;

3) "Statistics and Elements of Probability Theory" it is advisable to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in the teaching of materials for the educational unit;

4) General mathematical education is complete, it is an organized system. This system consists of a dialectical unity of five content lines, which can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. It should not be forgotten that systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity. The most common about whole and part from the point of view, a part is a component that is part of a system and has relative independence, a system that includes parts that are fully interconnected and contains some properties that are not always present in separate parts. so that

"Statistics and Elements of Probability Theory" materials for the educational unit "Statistics and probability" since it belongs to the content line, in the real pedagogical process, dialectical unity between the elements of both the whole (with the content covered by the subject of Mathematics as a whole) and the parts (subsystems of the other four content lines) belonging to each content line ("system-structure" approach-complete) -part relations) should be expected;

5) Expectation of the "opportunity-movement-quality" paradigm conditioned by the "system-structure" dialectical approach in the selection of tasks, making them into a system, has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

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